

Botnet Fingerprint Using Bro-IDS

Esraa Alshammari¹, Alaa H. Alhamami², Ali Hadi³

¹Department of Computer Science, Princess Sumaya University for Technology, Amman, Jordan

²College of Information and Communications Technology, British University of Bahrain, Bahrain.

³Champlain College, Burlington, Vermont.

¹israa88h@gmail.com, ²a.alhamami@bub.bh, ³ali@ashemery.com

Abstract— Botnets or robot networks are one of the most serious and widespread attacks in the network's era. This attack is used to enforce the control of the computers by injecting a small code into the computer to become one of the bots in the robot networks. Then the new bot will be linked with the supervisor or botmaster to get the instruction and commands that need to perform. Command and Control server (C&C) is the botmaster which sends the tasks to their connected bots. The motivations of using and launching such attacks are diverse from DDoS to spam, attacking IRC chat, spreading new malware, and gathering information... etc. Many of the botnet detection technique is based on the Intrusion Detection System (IDS) or Intrusion Prevention System (IPS), while the sophisticated technologies of the attackers are increasing to evade such system. Thus, the need for robust and advanced techniques is necessary due to the growth of the botnet attacks. In this paper, the main types and architecture for the botnet attacks will be presented. Additionally, the detection technique will be presented using Bro Monitoring tools in order to analyze in depth the network traffic, then detect the abnormal or malicious traffic that comes from the C&C server. This research considered as a step forward to detecting the botnet attack.

Keywords— Attacks, Botnet; Bro; Detection Techniques; Malware; Traffic Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of the technology especially related to the networks imposes new threats that exploit by intruders using a malware like a botnet to gain a control for any devices connected to the network.

The network's architecture should depend on a good security design that takes into consideration the new, serious and malicious attack such Botnet to defend itself and protect its secret data.

From last two decade until now, the botnet attack is the most harmful attacks that can exploits any available vulnerabilities exists in the traffic to perform their tasks. The bot network consists of many infected computers that act as a robot controlled by the botmaster server, or a command and control servers distributed among the world. The C&C servers are controlled their bots remotely by sending an instruction and commands using some well-known protocols to perform specific attacks [1, 2].

Botnet like other malware has a life cycle starting from searching for vulnerabilities inside the computers until maintaining the infections. The life cycle shown in

Figure 1, consists of five phases, the inspection phase, the injection phase, connection phase, malicious attack phase, and finally, the maintenance phase.

The first phase; the inspection phase; starts from the botmaster side, which inspect for a vulnerability of networks, web browsers or end user to exploits and joining the computers to the robots network. The second phase is Injection Phase, which begins to injecting a small code into the computers to deem the infected computer as a valid bot. The third phase; Connection phase. This phase starts from establishing the connection between the botmaster (C&C) and the infected computers by automatically executing the code that injected into the infected computer when it connects to the internet. The fourth step is the malicious attack which starts after the communication established between the bots and the C&C server, the server sends the commands and instruction for bots to achieving their tasks. Finally, the Maintaining Phase, which is the important phase to perpetuate the work of bots by supporting all bots in the network the updating codes, commands, and instruction to stay-in living and to detect any intrusion detection or prevention system [3].

Lack of awareness of security concepts and the procedures to defend for such malware leads to a significant threat which the botmaster can exploit it to launch a huge damage in the target. The common activities that the intruder performed with the bots are the Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack, Phishing attack, flooding attack, gathering information such as keyloggers to obtain the financial information about the user, and click fraud attack [4].

There is a number of tools that the organizations, individual users, and the researchers used to monitor their traffic and perform other tasks. One of the most common and powerful tools is Bro-IDS. Bro is an open source framework for network traffic analysis in depth that can analyze the traffic in real-time with high performance, efficient, and flexible manner [5].

The contribution of this research is to address the botnet types. Additionally, to detect one of the botnet types using Bro-IDS based on its logs. To the best of our knowledge, this research is the first attempt to detect the botnet attack using Bro-IDS logs.

Figure 1: Botnet Life Cycle

The rest of the research is organized as follows: Section II summarizes the related work on botnet detection. Section III illustrates the types of botnet attacks. While section IV present the proposed detection technique. Whereas Section V presents the discussions and results. Finally, conclusions and the future work will be discussed in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

Because the botnet is the harmful attacks, the researchers put most of their attention to understand the structure of the botnets, and how its work to detect it using the data mining techniques, machine learning, and traffic analysis.

In term of data mining techniques and machine learning algorithms, the author in [6] proposed a novel flow-based detection system which depends on supervised machine learning algorithms to detect the appearance of the bots in traffic originated from a well-known application. Additionally, the authors evaluate an eight supervised machine learning algorithms for classifying the botnet. The system has two phases, the pre-processing phase to obtain features from the network flow, and the classification phase to classify the network flow based on the extracted features. They obtained 39 different statistical features from the network flow, which they do not rely on the IP addresses, but purely based on the network flow, such as source port, destination port, duration, total number of bytes, and a total number of packets.....etc. Additionally, the eight supervised machine learning algorithms that chosen are: Naive Bayesian classifier (NB), Bayesian Network classifier (BNet), Logistic Regression (LR), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Support Vector Machines with linear kernel (SVMlin), C4.5 decision tree (C4.5), Random Tree classifier (RTree) and Random Forest classifier (RForest). The authors show that the only tree classifiers (C4.5, RTree, and RForest) have likely classification performances for botnet traffic.

In the same context of using a machine learning algorithms, the authors in [7] proposed a detection technique that relies on monitoring the traffic and then

use the judgment of the data mining techniques to improve the accuracy of the anomaly detection system. They select a Trojan. Peacomm virus as a research object to test their hypothesis. The authors have three main hypotheses that their detection system are based on it: set up many connections based on botnet structure. Keep the botnet on the transmission data to maintain the malicious activity. Finally, they use a minimum amount of data in the botnet communication to preserve the privacy. The authors achieve the following: 1. providing a detection method that proves its accuracy to detect the botnet attack. 2. Detecting the botnet regarding the traffic characteristics like encrypted or not. 3. A pre-warning review for the P2P botnet attack for the network behavior instead of post, which means there are no attacks.

Besides that, the authors in [8] proposed a scalable framework for implementing a quasi-real-time intrusion detection system build upon open source tools like Hadoop, Mahout, and Hive. The authors build a distributed framework using Hive for extracting features by sniffing and processing the traffic. Also, they use Mahout to build a Random Forest based Decision Tree model and applied to the P2P detection system. They illustrate the main component of the framework deeply which are: packet sniffer for preprocessing. Also for generating features, they used a feature extraction module and finally they used the machine learning algorithms for detecting the abnormal activity by learning the normal behavior. Finally, the authors conclude their work by providing a scalable framework for capturing the packets with high bandwidth of data within 5–30 s delay. Moreover, they provide a framework for P2P detection system that use the extracted features to classify the malicious traffic on a cluster.

Another method that using the data mining techniques is mentioned in [9] proposed a detection technique to detect the P2P botnet activity in real time by analyzing the characteristic of the traffic flow based on time interval. Additionally, proposed a methodology to classify the normal host from bot host. They classifying the network traffic behavior using a machine

learning classification techniques especially time interval method for extracting characteristics of the network flow in a small time window. This detection technique can be used to detect the existence of the botnet during the life cycle of the bot, or before the bot completes the tasks. The proposed algorithm works in the early stage before the bot performs the task by inspecting the traffic and analyze the TCP and UDP packets and payload for a signature of malicious software. Finally, the authors conclude their works by presents that the Bayesian network and the decision tree classifier both are proper for building a botnet detection framework based on the flow.

In [10], the authors classify the botnet detection techniques into six classes: honeypot based, signature-based, mining-based, anomaly-based, DNS-based and network-based. Additionally, they present a brief comparison between these classes. And finally, they discuss the honeypot based technique to detect the botnet and dealing with it. The authors also present that the detection techniques based on the signature will only detect a known botnet, rather than the other detection method. They conclude the importance of deploying a honeypot for detecting any type of botnet attack based on the architecture of the bots and the data mining or machine learning algorithms.

On the other hand, some researchers detect the botnet based on traffic analysis and monitoring. The authors in [11] proposed a new detection framework for general botnet based on passively monitoring network traffics that inspect the payload. The proposed framework has four phases: filtering phase, application classifier, malicious activity detector and traffic monitoring. Each phase has its functionality. The filtering phase for filtering the flow of the traffic to reduce the traffic workload. The application-classifier is used for separating the IRC and HTTP traffic from the remaining traffic. The malicious activity detector for analyze the traffic and try to detect the malicious activity by analyzing the behavior of the internal host. Finally, Traffic Monitoring is responsible for monitoring the traffic to detect the same behaviors and communication pattern of the group of the host, by checking the network traffic.

In [12] the authors proposed a complete testbed by implementing a real-time HTTP-based botnet which they performing a DDoS against web server by using flooding message i.e. HTTP-GET. Additionally, they trace the web access botnet in order to analyze and study the behavior of the HTTP botnet to provide a solution to detect such type. They used a virtual machine software to setup the system which used a client-server model by creating a 43 interconnected workstation runs on Windows Operating System. Although used 30 workstations for Windows XP S2, and 10 with windows 7 and one in S3. The authors install and use the HTTP-bot to perform the HTTP flood DDoS attacks against the Web server. The result of this testbed presents a sample result based on HTTP botnet in the form of tracing file

in order to understand the behavior of this type and detect it.

Additionally, the authors in [13] present a detection method to detect the Peer to Peer (P2P) botnet based on analysis of the network stream. The authors provide three algorithms: 1. P2P-nodes detection based on characteristics of paroxysm and distribution of the network streams. 2. P2P-nodes clustering that derived from the K-mean clustering algorithm to obtain the connection characteristic of the pair of nodes. 3. Botnet behavior similarity detection algorithm based on the suspicious actions of the bots. The researchers implement their detection method in Local Area Network (LAN) and extracting features from the net stream. Additionally, they present that the P2P botnet can be extracted from net stream and detect based on the characteristics of the paroxysm and distribution.

The researchers in [14] use Snort-IDS to detect the botnet attacks by providing a three rules packet. Additionally, they utilize the MCFP dataset that contains five files and providing their rules for these files. The rules techniques analyze the network traffic and obtain the patterns that Snort-IDS generated based on the networks traffic data behavior. The authors depend on some features or signatures in the traffic that if it exists, they claim that the bots have appeared. In fact, the attackers try to conceal themselves from any detection system that depends on the signatures by continuously creating a new bot that doesn't have the same characteristics from any other bot, which will change the signatures that the IDS detecting the attacks based on it.

III. THE BOTNET ARCHITECTURE

In this section, the main types of the botnet will be presented with a brief description of each one [15].

1. Centralized Botnet Architecture:

In this model all bots in the botnet network supervised by one master, therefore it is easy to manage and monitor botnet network but also it is easy to detect and prevent it. It based on IRC and HTTP for its C&C channel. There are many examples of centralized architecture such as; SDBot, GTBot, AgoBot, and SDBot. The centralized model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Centralized Botnet Architecture

2. Peer to Peer (P2P) Botnet Architecture:

According to centralized model weaknesses, attackers prefer a P2P model where each peer of bots act as supervisor and soldier bot, then each peer communicates with another peer in the network to transfer commands, which make botnet network more slowly. Each bot could be both supervisor and soldier bot.

The management and monitoring of this model are hard, but also the detection and prevention of it are hard. Phatbot and Peacomm are examples of P2P architecture. Figure 3 shows P2P model.

Figure 3: Peer-to-Peer Botnet Architecture

3. Hybrid Botnet Architecture:

As its name indicated, this model consists of two previous types: centralized and P2P architectures. For more security, the supervisor does not share any information about its own peer's list with other supervisors. This model is harder for detection and prevention. Figure 4 shows hybrid botnet architecture.

Figure 4: Hybrid Botnet Architecture

IV. THE PROPOSED DETECTION FRAMEWORK

In this section, the proposed framework presents how to detect the botnet based on Bro-IDS. The chosen traffic contains a Neris botnet with the MD5 (bf08e6b02e00d2bc6dd493e93e69872f), which is a centralized bot that contains spams, click fraud and port scanning sends to the target and runs for 6.15 hours. This type of bot used the HTTP as C&C channel to communicate with bots to send spam and then perform click-fraud. The dataset ISCX contains a pcap file with a size of 5.6GB of data. Also, the number of connection is 33,084. The botnet selected from traces in CTU13 datasets include Murlo, Neris, Rbot, Virut, which referred as captures 8, 9, 10, 13 respectively [16-20].

The selected trace inspected using a different tool, one of them is Wireshark, the open source tool for packet/traffic analyzer that can help the users to inspect their traffic and troubleshooting it [21]. There is some observation noticed while using the Wireshark, these are:

- The infected host have this IP address: 147.32.84.165
- Most of the actions that detected by Wireshark related to the TCP flags, such as (out of order

sequence, duplicate Ack, fast retransmission, or reset the connections) the Wireshark warning due to the errors detected in TCP flags.

- One of the most important observation is the truncated Get method that has an encrypted message or commands transmitted over HTTP using Get method.

Rather than using Wireshark, Bro-IDS used to analyze the traffic and obtains the logs to determine the appearance of the botnet or not.

Bro-IDS generate 10 logs file, these files are conn.log, dpd.log, files.log, pe.log, sip.log, smtp.log, snmp.log, ssl.log, weird.log, and x509.log. Table 1 shows the files with their descriptions [5].

Table1: Bro-IDS Logs

	Log File	Description	Field Descriptions
1	conn.log	TCP/UDP/ICMP connections	Conn::Info
2	files.log	File analysis results	Files::Info
3	pe.log	Portable Executable (PE)	PE::Info
4	x509.log	X.509 certificate info	X509::Info
5	weird.log	Unexpected network-level activity	Weird::Info
6	dpd.log	Dynamic protocol detection failures	DPD::Info
7	smtp.log	SMTP transactions	SMTP::Info
8	snmp.log	SNMP messages	SNMP::Info
9	ssl.log	SSL/TLS handshake info	SSL::Info
10	sip.log	SIP	SIP::Info

The conn.log file contains a source-IP, destination-IP, source port, and destination port, the protocol that used, and information about the connection. While the files.log contain other attributes that explain the files that transmitted via traffic with details about each file like duration, the total size of the file, and MIME type and more information to determine the files. Pe.log file is for portable executable files that transfer via the network between hosts. Also, this file has attributes to determine in depth the file and the users that send the file. The x509.log file contains all information related to the certificates like the algorithms used, hash value, the length of the key and the type of key...etc. While the snmp.log contains the whole information about the network management configuration that the host did to configure their devices, routers, printers, or switches ...etc. Also, Bro generate the smtp.log which contain the emails that transmitted via traffic, the source IP, port and email, and the destination IP, port, and email, with details about each email.

V. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

This section will discuss the differences between the proposed detection technique and the previous detection technique.

Most of the researchers have been appreciated the advantages of the data mining and machine learning techniques in the evaluation of their detection system. The authors in [6, 7, 8, and 9] applied the data mining techniques in order to detect the appearance of the bots in the traffic. Using of the data mining techniques gives the user benefits of detecting the bots based on some features they extracted from the traffic, but it's not necessary that the extracted features are correlated with each other which put the whole detection techniques in a challenge to extract more features about the traffic and the bot structure itself. While the trends are moving towards selecting technologies based on the behavior of the malware. This is the reason behind choosing the detection techniques based on the behavior of the traffic in this research.

While the authors in [11, 12, 13, and 14] analyzing the traffic to detect the appearance of the bots. The authors depend on the behavior of the bots to detect it, but most of them used the signatures of the bots, which is based on rules, if these rules check, the rules will generate the warning message of detection of bots, otherwise the detection will fail. These techniques will detect the will know bots with features determined in the early stage like the MD5, but can't detect the new behavior of the bots. Rather than using the proposed approach, it does not only detect the behavior of the known bots, but also any abnormal behavior will be detected and classified as weird traffic and need more inspection to determine it.

Besides that, the proposed detection system can detect any type of bots appeared in the traffic and generate logs with full details of the actions happened in the traffic. We believe that using Bro-IDS to detect the abnormal traffic especially the botnet malware is the first effort that concentrates on the behavior of suspicious content in the traffic.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Botnet malware became attractive threats for attackers to achieve their malicious intents according to the strength of the botnet. The Botnet considered as a first step to launch many other types of attacks such as DDoS attack, fishing attacks, and spams. Therefore, it's very important to be aware of the botnet and try to found the best solutions to protect or prevent your systems form such malware. This paper highlights the types of the botnet and its architecture for each type.

In addition to that, proposed a detection technique based on the behavior of the traffic using Bro-IDS and analyzing and observing the traffic using Wireshark.

This research is a step forward for other researchers whom an interest in detecting botnet malware based on the behavioral perspective of the network's traffic. In the next step, we attempt to take into consideration a real-

time traffic and apply the proposed techniques to ensure the accuracy of the detection technique.

References:

- [1] Search Security. (2017). What is botnet? - Definition from WhatIs.com. [Online] Available at: <http://searchsecurity.techtarget.com/definition/botnet> [Accessed 12 Jan. 2018].
- [2] Howtogeek.com. (2016). What Is a Botnet?. [Online] Available at: <https://www.howtogeek.com/183812/htg-explains-what-is-a-botnet/> [Accessed 12 Jan. 2018].
- [3] Wan, W., & Li, J. (2014, February). Investigation of state division in botnet detection model. In *Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT), 2014 16th International Conference on* (pp. 265-268). IEEE.
- [4] Feily, M., Shahrestani, A., & Ramadass, S. (2009, June). A survey of botnet and botnet detection. In *Emerging Security Information, Systems and Technologies, 2009. SECURWARE'09. Third International Conference on* (pp. 268-273). IEEE.
- [5] Bro.org. (2014). the Bro Network Security Monitor. [Online] Available at: <https://www.bro.org/> [Accessed 16 Jan. 2018].
- [6] Stevanovic, M., & Pedersen, J. M. (2014, February). An efficient flow-based botnet detection using supervised machine learning. In *Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC), 2014 International Conference on* (pp. 797-801). IEEE.
- [7] Liao, W. H., & Chang, C. C. (2010, August). Peer to peer botnet detection using data mining scheme. In *Internet Technology and Applications, 2010 International Conference on* (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [8] Singh, K., Guntuku, S. C., Thakur, A., & Hota, C. (2014). Big data analytics framework for peer-to-peer botnet detection using random forests. *Information Sciences*, 278, 488-497.
- [9] Zhao, D., Traore, I., Ghorbani, A., Sayed, B., Saad, S., & Lu, W. (2012). Peer to peer botnet detection based on flow intervals. *Information Security and Privacy Research*, 87-102.
- [10] Raghava, N. S., Sahgal, D., & Chandna, S. (2012, May). Classification of botnet detection based on botnet architecture. In *Communication Systems and Network Technologies (CSNT), 2012 International Conference on* (pp. 569-572). IEEE.
- [11] Zeidanloo, H. R., Manaf, A. B., Vahdani, P., Tabatabaei, F., & Zamani, M. (2010, June). Botnet detection based on traffic monitoring. In *Networking and Information Technology (ICNIT), 2010 International Conference on* (pp. 97-101). IEEE.
- [12] Alomari, E., Manickam, S., Gupta, B. B., Singh, P., & Anbar, M. (2014, February). Design, deployment and use of HTTP-based botnet (HBB) testbed. In *Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT), 2014 16th International Conference on* (pp. 1265-1269). IEEE.
- [13] Liu, D., Li, Y., Hu, Y., & Liang, Z. (2010, October). A P2P-botnet detection model and algorithms based on network streams analysis. In *Future Information Technology and Management Engineering (FITME), 2010 International Conference on* (Vol. 1, pp. 55-58). IEEE.
- [14] Chanthakoummane, Y., Saiyod, S., Benjamas, N., & Khamphakdee, N. (2016). Improving intrusion detection on snort rules for botnets detection. In *Information Science and Applications (ICISA) 2016* (pp. 765-779). Springer, Singapore.
- [15] Ullah, I., Khan, N., & Aboalsamh, H. A. (2013, April). Survey on botnet: Its architecture, detection, prevention and mitigation. In *Networking, Sensing and Control (ICNSC), 2013 10th IEEE International Conference on* (pp. 660-665). IEEE.
- [16] Le, D. C., Zincir-Heywood, A. N., & Heywood, M. I. (2016, December). Data analytics on network traffic flows for botnet behavior detection. In *Computational Intelligence (SSCI), 2016 IEEE Symposium Series on* (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
- [17] Beigi, E. B., Jazi, H. H., Stakhanova, N., & Ghorbani, A. A. (2014, October). Towards effective feature selection in machine learning-based botnet detection approaches. In *Communications and Network Security (CNS), 2014 IEEE Conference on* (pp. 247-255). IEEE.
- [18] Garcia, S. (2014). Identifying, Modeling and Detecting Botnet Behaviors in the Network (Doctoral dissertation, Universidad Nacional del Centro de la Provincia de Buenos Aires).
- [19] Alejandre, F. V., Cortés, N. C., & Anaya, E. A. (2016). Botnet Detection using Clustering Algorithms. *Research in Computing Science*, 118, 65-75.
- [20] Malware Capture facility project. (2011). CTU-Malware-Capture-Botnet-42. [Online] Available at: <https://mcfp.weebly.com/ctu-malware-capture-botnet-42.html> [Accessed 16 Jan. 2018].
- [21] Howtogeek.com. (2017). How to Use Wireshark to Capture, Filter and Inspect Packets. [online] Available at: <https://www.howtogeek.com/104278/how-to-use-wireshark-to-capture-filter-and-inspect-packets/> [Accessed 16 Jan. 2018].